

Environmental Sensitivities of Teacher Education Students in Two Countries on Different Continents

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Abstract

This study compared the environmental sensitivities of teacher education students in Nigeria and Turkey, examining the influence of grade level and gender. The survey included 342 Turkish and 344 Nigerian students, employing a three-point Likert scale "Environmental Sensitivity Questionnaire" ($\alpha=0.81$). Analysis involved frequency, arithmetic mean, Kruskal-Wallis H test, and Mann-Whitney U test in SPSS. Results revealed higher environmental sensitivity among Nigerian students, particularly males. Turkish students prioritized air pollution, while Nigerians focused on water pollution. No significant grade-level correlation was found in both countries, yet both showed partial sensitivity to air pollution. Environmental education was perceived as inadequate by students in both nations. Recommendations include curriculum enhancement and reorientation on issues like population growth, ecological balance, and pollution.

Keywords: *Teacher education student, environment, environmental awareness, environmental sensitivity, climate change.*

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Introduction

Environment encompasses the natural and social surroundings within which organisms and communities exist, shaped by a dynamic interplay of living and non-living elements, including atmosphere, water, soil, vegetation, animals, and humans (Akyüz, 2020; Bernhardt et al., 2020; Eryılmaz, 2019). The natural environment comprises ecosystems like forests, seas, rivers, and deserts, providing fundamental necessities such as sustenance, water, oxygen, and habitat for living entities. Meanwhile, the social environment pertains to the societal framework influenced by cultural, economic, political, and religious factors, encompassing human interactions and social norms (Chawla, 2020; Li et al., 2021; Marselle et al., 2019). Recognizing the vital link between a healthy natural environment and human well-being is crucial. A balanced focus on both environmental and social aspects in values education is essential. Environmental awareness involves understanding and actively addressing responsibilities towards sustainability, resource conservation, and pollution reduction. This includes actions like recycling, energy conservation, and using eco-friendly products, all contributing to efforts in protecting nature and fostering a more sustainable world. Environmental awareness transcends individual actions, representing a societal imperative, prompting large-scale organizations, including businesses, governmental bodies, and local governments, to embrace environmental concerns and champion sustainability (Ekpo & Olatunde-Aiyedun, 2019; Eneji et al., 2021; Okada et al., 2019; Pihkala, 2020). The 21st century has witnessed a surge in environmental awareness, bolstered by international agreements on environmental issues, with educational institutions assuming a pivotal role in fostering environmental awareness by equipping students with knowledge of environmental issues and eco-conscious behaviors to nurture a more environmentally aware and hospitable world (Çabuk & Karacaoğlu, 2003; Borchers et al., 2014; Daubenmire et al., 2017; Değirmenci et al., 2023; Erdem et al., 2019; Gıdır et al., 2020; Kurt Konakoğlu, 2020; Nesmith et al., 2016; Okada et al., 2019; Soğukpınar & Karışan Korucu, 2020; Yeşil & Turan, 2020; Yeşilyurt et al., 2020).

Creating environmental sensitivity in teacher candidates has a special importance as they are the educators of the future who can influence the environmental attitudes and behaviors of future generations. The environmental sensitivity of teachers is important not only for individual consciousness but also for social transformation (Karacaoğlu & Karacaoğlu, 2023). Studies conducted on physics teachers reveal that the level of environmental sensitivity is directly related to course content and teacher identity. Research in this domain has revealed variations in teacher education students' environmental sensitivity, influenced by factors like personal beliefs, attitudes towards the environment, grade level, prior environmental education, and sociocultural background (Avarogullari et al., 2019; Bağçeli Kahraman et al., 2019; Brandt et al.; Duru, 2022; Eneji et al., 2021; Eze, 2020; Kadioğlu Ateş & Işık Öner, 2020; Kahyaoğlu & Özgen, 2012; Karadağ & Acar, 2020; McKeown-Ice, 2000; Olatunde-Aiyedun & Ogunode, 2021; Özonur, 2021; Öztarakçı, 2019; Patonah et al., 2018; Tuncer, 2021; Türksever, 2021; Semenderoğlu & Arslan, 2022; Van Petegem et al., 2007). Teacher education programs play a crucial role in cultivating environmental sensitivity in students and society (Karacaoğlu & Özkaya, 2023). By integrating environmental

education into their curricula, these programs equip future teachers with knowledge and skills to address environmental issues in their teaching. Beyond information dissemination, emphasis should be on fostering critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. Promoting environmental sensitivity among teacher education students is essential for nurturing environmentally conscious generations and ensuring a sustainable future. Notably, the environmental challenges faced by Nigeria and Turkey (Bozoglu et al., 2022; Mashi et al., 2021; Nurwidodo et al., 2020; Sinan et al., 2022) underscore the importance of pre-service teacher environmental sensitivity. Comparing the environmental sensitivity of pre-service teachers in these countries offers insights into their environmental knowledge and sensitivities, reflecting the distinctions and commonalities in their education systems and contextual backgrounds, given the diverse environmental issues influenced by varying cultures, geography, and economic structures. Environmental sensitivity is an important issue that needs to be addressed in teacher education programs. Teacher education students should be aware of environmental issues and their impact on the planet to prepare them to teach future generations the importance of sustainability. Research shows that pre-service teachers in both Nigeria and Turkey show interest in environmental issues (Bozoglu et al, 2022; Mashi et al, 2021; Nurwidodo et al, 2020; Sinan et al, 2022). However, some differences can be seen between pre-service teachers' knowledge of environmental issues and their environmental sensitivity (Brandt et al, 2019; Cengiz, 2022; Çavuşoğlu, 2019; Çelik & Doğru, 2019; Duru, 2022; Eneji et al 2021; Eze, 2020). It can be seen when previous studies are examined that environmental education and awareness studies should be further developed in both countries and the level of pre-service teachers' knowledge on environmental issues should be increased. With the assumption that pre-service teachers can be more sensitive to environmental issues as future educators and can raise awareness about environmental issues among their students, it was deemed important to examine teacher education students. For this reason, the level of environmental sensitivity of teacher education students in Nigeria and Turkey, their similarities and differences in terms of environmental sensitivity, and reasons for those similarities and differences were seen as problems in the research.

In this study, which aims to compare the environmental sensitivity of teacher education students in Nigeria and Turkey, the following questions were sought to be answered:

1. What is the level of environmental sensitivity of Teacher Education Students in Turkey and Nigeria?
2. What is the environmental sensitivity of teacher education students in Turkey and Nigeria regarding air pollution, water pollution, soil pollution, ecological balance and participation in environmental studies?
3. What are the views of teacher education students on environmental education in Turkey and Nigeria?
4. Is there a difference between the environmental awareness of teacher education students in Turkey and Nigeria and the country variable?
5. Is there a relationship between the environmental awareness of teacher education students in Turkey and Nigeria and their gender and grade level?
6. Is there a difference between the views of students in Nigeria and Turkey on the environmental education they receive?

Materials and Methods

Comparative quantitative research methods were used in the study. The research is descriptive as it reveals the current situation.

Study Groups

The study was conducted with teacher education students studying at the faculties of education in a selected university in South East Nigeria and southeast Turkey. In Turkey, the research was conducted on the students of Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Faculty of Education while in Nigeria, teacher education students in the Faculty of Education, Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu-Alike Ebonyi State, Nigeria participated in the study. Generally, 342 teacher education students from Turkey and 344 teacher education students from Nigeria who answered the questionnaire voluntarily.

Data Collection

In this study, we utilized Çabuk and Karacaoğlu (2003) "Environmental Sensitivity Questionnaire" to assess and compare the environmental sensitivity of teacher education students in Nigeria and Turkey. The questionnaire comprises 24 questions, validated through expert opinions and a preliminary application with a reliability level (α) of 0.81 in Turkish and 0.79 in Nigerian groups. A factor analysis test was employed for sub-factor validity. The questionnaire, with three rating scales ("Always," "Sometimes," and "Never"), was electronically distributed via a Google Form link, translated into Turkish and English. Students gave consent on the first page, and only consenting students proceeded to provide biodata before answering the questions. The questionnaire was accessible for six weeks, followed by data analysis after closing the link.

Data analysis

According to the results of the environmental sensitivity scores (Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test) obtained from the groups, it was determined that the scores of Nigeria and Turkey were not parametric ($p < .05$). Therefore, it was decided to use nonparametric tests to analyze the data.

Table 1. Normality Test Results of Environmental Sensitivity Questionnaire by Countries

Test	Country	Statistic	Df	p
Environmental Sensitivity Survey	Nigeria	.093	344	.000
	Turkey	.084	342	.000

In examining the environmental sensitivity scores based on gender, as detailed in Table 1, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test revealed non-parametric distribution for both male and female participants in both countries ($p < .05$). This non-parametric nature of the data guided the decision to employ suitable nonparametric tests for subsequent analyses.

Table 2. Normality Test Results of Environmental Sensitivity Questionnaire by Gender of Countries

Test	Country/Gender	Statistic	Df	p
Environmental Sensitivity Survey	Nigeria/Woman	.095	101	.025
	Nigeria/Male	.098	243	.000
	Turkey/Female	.107	241	.000
	Turkey/Male	.097	101	.020

The results of the environmental sensitivity scores (Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test) obtained from the groups according to grade levels are given in Table 2. It was determined that the environmental awareness scores of Nigeria 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th graders and Turkey 1st and 2nd graders were not parametric ($p < .05$). It was concluded that the environmental awareness scores of Turkey 3rd and 4th grade students were parametric ($p > .05$). Therefore, it was decided to use nonparametric tests to analyze the data.

Table 3. Normality Test Results of the Environmental Sensitivity Questionnaire According to the Grade Levels of the Countries

Test	Country/Class Level	Statistic	df	p
Environmental Sensitivity Survey	Nigeria/1st Class	.120	92	.002
	Nigeria/2nd Grade	.096	98	.026
	Nigeria/3rd Grade	.097	97	.025
	Nigeria/4th Grade	.140	57	.007
	Turkey/1st Class	.131	92	.001
	Turkey/2nd Grade	.091	98	.046
	Turkey/3rd Grade	.083	98	.089
	Turkey/4th Grade	.105	54	.200*

The data obtained from 342 teacher education students from Turkey and 344 teacher education students from Nigeria in the study group were analyzed and the findings were obtained and presented in Table 3. The findings were interpreted using frequency, arithmetic mean and percentages.

In order to examine the environmental sensitivities of teacher education students in the earthquake region, data were interpreted using frequency, percentage and arithmetic averages. While entering the survey data, 3 values were given for always, 2 values for sometimes and 1 value for never. Therefore, arithmetic averages were between 1 and 3. The arithmetic mean of the obtained data was interpreted according to the following ranges:

- 1.00 to 1.66 : Low level of environmental sensitivity
- 1.67 to 2.32 : Moderate environmental sensitivity / partial sensitivity
- 2.33 to 3.00 : High level of environmental sensitivity

Results

To assess the environmental sensitivities of teacher education students in Turkey and Nigeria, including their perspectives on air, water, and soil pollution, ecological

balance, participation in environmental studies, and views on environmental education, descriptive statistics were analyzed in the following tables (Appendix).

As seen in Table 4 (Appendix), Nigerian teacher education students had a mean score of 2.29 for questions about air pollution, and Turkish students scored 2.31. This suggests that teacher education students in both countries exhibit partial sensitivity to environmental concerns related to air pollution, with scores closely aligned.

As shown in Table 5 (Appendix), Nigerian teacher education students had a higher mean score of 2.48 for questions about water pollution, while Turkish students scored 2.26. This indicates that Nigerian students exhibited high sensitivity to environmental issues related to water pollution, whereas Turkish students showed partial sensitivity in this regard.

Table 6 (Appendix) reveals that the mean scores for answers given by teacher education students in Nigeria and Turkey to questions about soil pollution are both 1.47. This indicates a low level of environmental sensitivity among teacher education students in both countries regarding soil pollution.

Table 7 (Appendix) indicates that the mean scores for all questions related to ecological balance are closely aligned. The mean score for Nigerian teacher education students is 1.82, and for Turkish students, it is 1.80. This suggests that the environmental sensitivity of teacher education students in both countries regarding ecological balance is at a medium level, indicating partial sensitivity to environmental aspects related to ecological balance.

As shown in Table 8 (Appendix), the mean scores for Nigerian and Turkish teacher education students regarding participation in environmental studies are 1.52 and 1.51, respectively. This indicates that students in both countries have similar and low levels of sensitivity towards participation in environmental studies.

In Table 9 (Appendix), it is seen that the arithmetic mean of the answers given by teacher education students in Nigeria to the questions about environmental education is 1.51, while in Turkey it is 1.51. It is seen that teacher education students in both countries do not believe that they have received adequate environmental education. teacher education students in each country see environmental education in their countries as inadequate.

In order to find the answer to the question "Is there a difference between the environmental sensitivity of teacher education students in Turkey and Nigeria and the country variable?" Mann-Whitney U test, one of the nonparametric tests, was conducted and the results are given in Table 10.

Table 10. Mann-Whitney U Analysis Results of Environmental Sensitivity by Country

Countries	n	Rank Mean	Queue Total	Z	p
Nigeria	344	366.96	126234.00	-3.119	.002
Turkey	342	319.90	109407.00		
Total	686				

When Table 10 is examined, it is found that there is a significant difference between environmental sensitivity scores according to countries ($z=-3.119, p<.05$). Considering the rank averages, it is seen that the environmental sensitivity scores of Nigerian

students (366.96) are significantly higher than the environmental sensitivity scores of teacher education students in Turkey (319.90).

In order to find the answer to the question "Is there a relationship between the environmental sensitivities of teacher education students in Turkey and Nigeria and their gender?" Kruskal-Wallis H test, one of the nonparametric tests, was conducted and the results are given in Table 11.

Table 11. Kruskal-Wallis H Test Analysis Results of Comparison of Environmental sensitivity by Gender of Teacher Education Students in Nigeria and Turkey

Gender	n	Rank Mean	sd	X ²	p	Significant Difference
Nigeria/Woman	101	318.12	3	23.208	.000	Nigeria/Male>Nigeria/Female Nigeria/Male>Turkey/Female Nigeria/Male>Turkey/Female Nigeria/Male>Turkey/Male
Nigeria/Male	243	387.26				
Turkey/Female	241	334.97				
Turkey/Male	101	283.96				
Total	686					

Examining Table 11 reveals significant differences in environmental sensitivity scores among teacher education students based on gender ($X^2(3) = 23.208, p < .05$). Mann Whitney U tests showed significant differences between Nigerian men and women ($Z = -3.019, p < .008$), Nigerian men and Turkish women ($Z = -2.928, p < .008$), and Nigerian men and Turkish men ($Z = -4.319, p < .008$). Nigerian male students had significantly higher environmental sensitivity scores (mean rank: 387.26) compared to Nigerian females (318.12), Turkish females (334.97), and Turkish males (283.96). In Nigeria, male teacher education students are more environmentally sensitive than females, while in Turkey, female students exhibit higher environmental sensitivity than males.

In order to find the answer to the question "Is there a relationship between the environmental sensitivities of teacher education students in Turkey and Nigeria and their grade levels?" Kruskal-Wallis H test, another nonparametric tests, was conducted and the results are given in Table 12.

Table 12. Kruskal-Wallis H Test Analysis Results of the Comparison of Environmental Sensitivity According to the Grade Levels of Teacher Education Students in Nigeria and Turkey

Grade Levels of Countries	n	Rank Mean	Sd	X ²	p
Nigeria/1st Grade	92	380.51	7	12.704	.080
Nigeria/2nd Grade	98	367.96			
Nigeria/3rd Grade	97	366.04			
Nigeria/4th Grade	57	344.92			
Turkey/1st Grade	92	336.43			
Turkey/2nd Grade	98	319.71			
Turkey/3rd Grade	98	320.71			
Turkey/4th Grade	54	290.64			
Total	686				

Examining Table 12 reveals no significant differences in environmental sensitivity scores among teacher education students based on their grade levels ($X^2(7)=12.704$, $p>.05$). Mean ranks for Nigerian students ranged from 344.92 to 380.51, and for Turkish students from 290.64 to 344.92. This suggests no correlation between grade level and environmental sensitivity scores, indicating that education at the faculty of education in both countries has no discernible impact on environmental sensitivity.

Discussion

The research findings were analyzed to determine environmental sensitivities among teacher education students in Turkey and Nigeria concerning air, water, and soil pollution, ecological balance, participation in environmental studies, and views on environmental education. Comparisons were made based on gender and grade level within and between the two countries, leading to discussions and conclusions.

Nigerian teacher education students have higher environmental sensitivity than their Turkish counterparts. The higher environmental sensitivity of Nigerian teacher education students is in tandem with Ayalande and Olusolape (2016) who reported of a good understanding of climate change environmental sensitivity among Nigerian university students. Though their study was generally on University students, teacher education students are part of their population. Koçulu (2018) concluded that science teacher education students in Turkey have high awareness of sustainable development, have positive attitudes towards environmental problems, but their behaviors towards environmental problems are at a moderate level. This result supports the conclusion that the environmental sensitivity of teacher education students in Turkey is not high. Findings of the study conducted by Ekpo & Olatunde-Aiyedun (2019) emphasize that environmental education should raise awareness about adaptation to climate change in Nigeria, and for this, it should be emphasized in primary, secondary and higher education institutions as well as in rural and urban settlements. Ogunyemi and Ifegbesan (2011) found high levels of awareness/knowledge of local environmental issues among teacher education students in a Nigerian university, but low levels of awareness/knowledge of global environmental issues. Although there is a positive disposition towards environmental issues in Nigeria, it is emphasized that there is a lack of knowledge that can hinder environmental management.

Nigerian male teacher education students show higher environmental sensitivity than their female counterparts and Turkish peers. In Nigeria, male students are more sensitive than females, while in Turkey, female students exhibit greater sensitivity than males. Turkish students prioritize air pollution, while Nigerians focus on water pollution. Both groups show less sensitivity towards soil pollution. Grade levels in teacher education programs do not correlate with environmental sensitivity in either country. This suggests a need for a review of education faculty and teacher education curricula in terms of environmental education.

Studies examining environmental sensitivity according to different variables have been conducted before. The result of Ogunbode and Arnold (2012) and Eneji et al (2021) that male teacher educators in Nigeria have higher environmental sensitivity is similar. The findings of the studies conducted by Çabuk and Karacaoğlu (2003), Kayalı (2013) and Torun et al (2023) support the conclusion that female teacher education students in Turkey are more sensitive than male students. On the other hand, in the research conducted by Aydın et al (2011) and Değirmen (2020) with participants who were not teacher education students, no relationship was found between environmental

sensitivity and gender. In the study conducted by Pirincci et al (2020) with health vocational school students, it was found that male students were more sensitive than female students. Accordingly, it was concluded that the result that female students among teacher education students are more sensitive to the environment cannot be generalized to students studying in other programs. Likewise, Pirincci et al (2020) emphasized that those who study in programs with high university entrance points have a higher level of environmental sensitivity. In the study conducted by Yılmaz and Arslan (2011), a relationship was found between environmental sensitivity and gender, place of residence and parents' education level. Kanbak (2015) aimed to measure the environmental attitudes and behaviors of university students and examined whether there were significant differences among students according to variables such as environmental course, age, gender, grade level, place of residence, parental education and parental occupation. As a result of the study, it was found that gender, environmental course, place of residence, mother's education level and mother's occupation did not make a difference in determining attitudes, whereas age, father's occupation, father's education level and students' grade level made a difference. In our study, it was determined that there was no difference in the environmental sensitivity of both Nigerian and Turkish teacher education students in terms of class levels. This result is contrary to the findings of Çabuk and Karacaoğlu (2003) and Torun et al (2023). According to Çabuk and Karacaoğlu (2003), fourth grade teacher education students have higher environmental sensitivity than students in other grades. When environmental problems and issues are adequately addressed in teacher education, the expected result is that environmental sensitivity increases as the grade level increases. However, neither in Nigeria nor in Turkey do the environmental sensitivities of teacher education students differ according to grade level. It is thought-provoking that teacher education programs do not affect environmental sensitivity in both countries.

Teacher education students in both countries are partially sensitive to the environment regarding air pollution. Regarding air pollution, it was determined that teacher education students in Nigeria did not tend to use public transportation related to environmental sensitivity. On the other hand, students in Turkey were not sensitive to the use of consumer goods containing substances harmful to the ozone layer. Nigerian students were more sensitive to noise pollution while Turkish students were more sensitive to bad emissions into the air. It was concluded that teacher education students in both Nigeria and Turkey were least sensitive to warning other people about air pollution. Students in both countries are partially sensitive to warning other people about air pollution. Pirincci et al (2020) found that the most important environmental problems in the world are air pollution, overuse of natural resources and unplanned settlement/migration/global warming, respectively. According to Oğuz et al (2011), the emphasis on air pollution as the most important environmental problem and Gill et al's (2018) studies on the importance of energy pollution make it compulsory to include content on air pollution in curricula.

Regarding water pollution, teacher education students in Nigeria have high environmental sensitivity. teacher education students in Turkey are partially sensitive to water pollution. teacher education students in Nigeria were found to purchase more harmful cleaning materials, while students in Turkey were found to be less sensitive in warning other people about water use. Teacher education students in both countries have high environmental sensitivity on frugality in water use and water conservation. Pirincci et al (2020) emphasized that students care about water consumption and water pollution problems and are more sensitive about them. Most studies on climate change and the environment highlight the importance of sensitivity to water pollution,

emphasizing that climate change is expected to have a very serious impact on water resources, water conservation, water reuse and food productivity. (Eneji et al, 2021; Nesmith et al, 2016; Sandhaus et al, 2019).

The environmental sensitivity of teacher education students in Turkey and Nigeria regarding soil pollution is low. It was determined that the least sensitivity of teacher education students in both Nigeria and Turkey regarding soil pollution was planting saplings (seedlings) by taking into account the appropriate conditions for the subject to grow. In both countries, environmental sensitivity about planting saplings is low. In a study conducted twenty years ago by Çabuk and Karacaoğlu (2003) with the same questionnaire, it was emphasized that teacher education students planted saplings from time to time considering the appropriate conditions. According to these two findings obtained twenty years apart, there has not been a positive development in the sensitivity of teacher education students in Turkey towards tree planting. On the other hand, teacher education students in Nigeria were found to be more sensitive about planting trees, while students in Turkey were found to be relatively less sensitive. In addition, teacher education students in both countries were found to have low environmental sensitivity about the use of paper. It is clear that teacher education students, who will assume important roles in society in the future, should be more protective and attentive to the soil, which is an important source of life (Gürten & Köseoğlu, 2019).

Teacher education students in Turkey and Nigeria were found to be partially sensitive to the environment in relation to ecological balance. In both countries, it was determined that the sensitivity to pay attention to population planning by considering the ecological balance was low. This can be thought to be due to the population policies implemented in the countries and the encouraging management approaches to increase the young population. It was determined that teacher education students in Nigeria reacted more to experiments on animals, while students in Turkey were more moderate towards these experiments. Both countries have low sensitivity to warn others about the protection of ecological balance. Perhaps the most important reason for this is that all over the world, individualism has taken precedence over socialization and thinking about social benefit. However, today, with the increasing world population, unplanned industrialization and the impact of humanity, the environment has started to consume itself. Environmental problems such as global warming, deterioration in ecological balance, extinction of living things and water shortage have gained importance as they started to harm humanity (Karahan et al, 2017). While the individual's views on warning others and environmental education are related to environmental sensitivity, his/her own perceptions of environmental issues and problems are related to environmental sensitivity. While environmental sensitivity refers to the ability to empathise and react emotionally towards others, environmental sensitivity refers to the capacity to consciously perceive and understand one's inner and outer world. These two concepts complement each other and are important in terms of human social relations, personal development and general quality of life.

The sensitivity of teacher education students in Turkey and Nigeria regarding participation in environmental studies is low. Regarding participation in environmental studies, it was determined that teacher education students in Nigeria participated in scientific studies such as seminars, panels and conferences on the environment relatively more than Turkish students, while teacher education students in Turkey participated in the activities of voluntary organizations working on the environment relatively more than Nigerian students. Despite this difference, students in both

countries do not participate sufficiently in environmental studies. Supporting this finding, Mansaray et al (1998) found that most teachers in Nigeria had never heard of environmental education and had never attended any workshops or seminars on teaching the subject. This assertion however, has recorded a slight improvement from “never heard of” to “low” given recent findings; e.g. Eze et al’s (2022) report of teachers’ low to moderate climate science literacy and the expressed needs for training on climate change concepts. In Turkey, the majority of teacher education students stated that they sometimes participate in scientific activities such as seminars, panels and conferences on the environment (Çabuk and Karacaoğlu, 2003).

Teacher education students in Nigeria and Turkey believe that the education they receive is not sufficient in terms of air, water, soil and ecological balance. It has been determined that teacher education students in Nigeria and Turkey do not believe that they receive sufficient environmental education. Sustainability practices in lower age groups can positively affect students' environmental awareness (Karacaoğlu, 2024). This finding shows that education for prospective teachers should be structured starting from an earlier age. The findings of Eze et al, (2022) affirmed the inadequate science literacy of the secondary school training hence, the dire training need on climate change concepts. Similarly, the findings of the study by Olatunde-Aiyedun & Ogunode (2021) on shortage of professional science and environmental education teachers in Nigeria revealed that the problem of shortage of professional science and environmental education teachers is prevalent in all educational institutions in Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended that environmental education concepts should be taught by qualified environmental education teachers and lecturers in science courses at all levels of education from primary to higher education in Nigeria. Demir and Yalçın (2014) emphasized that in Turkey, there is no specific environmental education policy for higher education that is established and implemented at the national level, which supports the results of this study on environmental education in Turkey. They found that university students in Turkey generally learn about the environment from print and visual media. Taken together, these findings show that print and visual media play an effective role in creating environmental sensitivity. Likewise, in studies conducted at the high school level, a significant number of students think that they have not received sufficient education in formal education institutions on air pollution, water pollution, soil pollution and ecological balance (Aydın et al, 2011). Teacher education students in both countries see environmental education in their countries as inadequate. Obviously, there are problems related to environmental education in both Nigeria and Turkey. Both countries should develop national policies and curricula to solve these problems. Regarding environmental education, students in Nigeria believe that they receive the least education on water pollution, while students in Turkey believe that they receive the least education on air pollution. The development of environmental education curricula that take into account all dimensions, including climate change, global warming, and disaster management, prioritizing air pollution in Turkey and water pollution in Nigeria, should be prioritized rapidly. The recommendation made by Agboola and Emmanuel (2016) for restructuring climate change education for Nigeria and embedding it in the curricula of schools at all levels and educating, empowering or enlightening the public and stakeholders on climate change is applicable to both Turkey and Nigeria for environmental education and environmental sensitization.

Conclusion

Based on the results and discussions presented above, the conclusions drawn from the research are as follows:

1. Environmental sensitivity among teacher education students in Nigeria surpasses that of their Turkish counterparts. This variance underscores the need for tailored environmental education strategies in each country.
2. Nigerian male teacher education students exhibit greater environmental sensitivity compared to their female counterparts and Turkish peers, while Turkish female students demonstrate higher sensitivity than Turkish males. These gender-based differences emphasize the importance of considering cultural contexts in environmental education initiatives.
3. Grade levels within teacher education programs do not significantly influence environmental sensitivity in either Nigeria or Turkey, suggesting a need for comprehensive reviews of environmental education curricula and teaching methodologies.
4. Both Nigerian and Turkish teacher education students display partial sensitivity towards environmental issues such as air, water, soil pollution, and ecological balance. However, there are notable disparities in their sensitivities towards specific environmental concerns, highlighting the importance of targeted educational interventions.
5. Participation in environmental studies among teacher education students in both countries remains inadequate, indicating a gap in environmental education initiatives and opportunities for student engagement.
6. Despite recognizing the inadequacies of their environmental education, teacher education students in Nigeria and Turkey believe that their current educational curricula fail to adequately address key environmental issues. This underscores the urgent need for policy reforms and curriculum enhancements to integrate comprehensive environmental education at all levels of education.
7. Recommendations include the development of national policies and curricula tailored to address the specific environmental concerns of each country, such as prioritizing air pollution education in Turkey and water pollution education in Nigeria. Additionally, restructuring environmental education to include climate change concepts and embedding them within school curricula at all levels is crucial for fostering environmental literacy and sensitization among students and stakeholders.

In conclusion, the research findings underscore the importance of enhancing environmental education initiatives in both Nigeria and Turkey to cultivate a generation of environmentally conscious citizens capable of addressing pressing environmental challenges.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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Appendix

Table 4. Environmental Sensitivity of Teacher Education Students in Nigeria and Turkey on Air Pollution

Questions	Always				Sometimes				Never				Nigeria	Turkey
	Nigeria		Turkey		Nigeria		Turkey		Nigeria		Turkey			
	n	%	N	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	\bar{x}	\bar{x}
1. Are you careful not to use consumer goods (deodorants and other sprays) that contain substances harmful to the ozone layer?	71	20.6	59	17.3	238	69.2	216	63.2	35	10.2	67	19.6	2.10	1.98
2. Even if you own your own car, do you use public transportation, taking into account the need to avoid air pollution?	60	17.4	255	74.6	217	63.1	80	23.4	67	19.5	7	2.0	1.98	2.73
3. When you talk and use various tools, do you take care that other people are not affected?	264	76.7	138	40.4	73	21.2	179	52.3	7	2.0	25	7.3	2.75	2.33
4. Do you warn people to be sensitive about air pollution?	134	39.0	114	33.3	185	53.8	185	54.1	25	7.3	43	12.6	2.32	2.21
Total	$N_{\text{Nigeria}}=344$ $N_{\text{Turkey}}=342$											2.29	2.31	

Table 5. Environmental Sensitivities of Teacher Education Students in Nigeria and Turkey Regarding Water Pollution

Questions	Always				Sometimes				Never				Nigeria	Turkey
	Nigeria		Turkey		Nigeria		Turkey		Nigeria		Turkey			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	\bar{x}	\bar{x}
5. Do you buy cleaning products with an eye on whether they contain harmful chemicals?	114	33.1	195	57	187	54.4	145	42.4	43	12.5	2	0.6	2.21	2.56
6. Are you frugal in water use in all circumstances?	201	58.4	222	64.9	141	41.0	108	31.6	2	0.6	12	3.5	2.58	2.61
7. Do you take care to prevent harmful chemicals such as engine oil and paint from entering the sewage system?	224	65.1	184	53.8	108	31.4	149	43.6	12	3.5	9	2.6	2.62	2.51
8. Do you warn people to be sensitive about water pollution?	185	53.8	5	1.5	150	43.6	108	31.6	9	2.6	229	67.0	2.51	1.35
Total	$N_{\text{Nigeria}}=344$ $N_{\text{Turkey}}=342$												2.48	2.26

Table 6. Environmental Sensitivities of Teacher Education Students in Nigeria and Turkey Regarding Soil Pollution

Questions	Always				Sometimes				Never				Nigeria	Turkey
	Nigeria		Turkey		Nigeria		Turkey		Nigeria		Turkey			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	\bar{x}	\bar{x}
9. Do you take care to use both sides of the paper you write on?	6	1.7	7	2.0	107	31.1	135	39.5	231	67.2	200	58.5	1.35	1.44
10. Are you frugal in using paper napkins in all circumstances?	5	1.5	6	1.8	137	39.8	204	59.6	202	58.7	132	38.6	1.43	1.63
11. Do you plant seedlings taking into account the conditions suitable for their growth?	1	0.3	2	0.6	210	61.0	85	24.9	133	38.7	255	74.6	1.62	1.26
12. Do you make sure that the waste reaches the garbage bin?	6	1.7	7	2.0	81	23.5	156	45.6	257	74.7	179	52.3	1.27	1.50
13. Do you dispose of waste in the appropriate recycling bins so that it can be recycled?	3	0.9	3	0.9	160	46.5	217	63.5	181	52.6	122	35.7	1.48	1.65
14. Do you classify garbage when you throw it away?	1	0.3	2	0.6	219	63.7	171	50.0	124	36.0	169	49.4	1.64	1.51
15. Do you warn people around you to be sensitive about soil pollution?	4	1.2	5	1.5	168	48.8	88	25.7	172	50.0	249	72.8	1.51	1.29
Total	$N_{\text{Nigeria}}=344$ $N_{\text{Turkey}}=342$												1.47	1.47

Table 7. Environmental Sensitivities of Teacher Education Students in Nigeria and Turkey Regarding Ecological Balance

Questions	Always				Sometimes				Never				Nigeria	Turkey
	Nigeria		Turkey		Nigeria		Turkey		Nigeria		Turkey			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	\bar{x}	\bar{x}
16. If you were/are married, would you pay attention to population planning by considering ecological balance?	4	1.2	4	1.2	89	25.9	110	32.2	251	73.0	228	66.7	1.28	1.35
17. For the sake of humanity, do you approve of any kind of experimentation on humans and animals?	234	68	171	50.0	110	32.0	170	49.7	0	0	1	0.3	2.68	2.50
18. Do you warn people around you to be sensitive about the protection of ecological balance?	3	0.9	3	0.9	171	49.7	186	54.4	170	49.4	153	44.7	1.51	1.56
Total	$N_{Nigeria}=344$ $N_{Turkey}=342$												1.82	1.80

Table 8. Environmental Sensitivities of Teacher Education Students in Nigeria and Turkey towards Participation in Environmental Studies

Questions	Always				Sometimes				Never				Nigeria	Turkey
	Nigeria		Turkey		Nigeria		Turkey		Nigeria		Turkey			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	\bar{x}	\bar{x}
19. Do you participate in scientific studies such as seminars, panels, conferences on the environment?	0	0	0	0	187	54.4	170	49.7	157	45.6	172	50.3	1.54	1.50
20. Do you participate in the activities of voluntary organizations working on the environment?	0	0	0	0	172	50.0	173	50.6	172	50.0	169	49.4	1.50	1.51
Total	$N_{\text{Nigeria}}=344$ $N_{\text{Turkey}}=342$												1.52	1.51

Table 9. Environmental Sensitivities of Teacher Education Students in Nigeria and Turkey Regarding Environmental Education

Questions	Yes				Partially				No				Nigeria	Turkey
	Nigeria		Turkey		Nigeria		Turkey		Nigeria		Turkey			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	\bar{x}	\bar{x}
21. Do you believe that you have received enough training to raise awareness about air pollution?	0	0	0	0	172	50.0	165	48.2	172	50.0	177	51.8	1.50	1.48
22. Do you believe that you have received sufficient training to raise awareness about water pollution?	0	0	0	0	168	48.8	171	50.0	176	51.2	171	50.0	1.49	1.50
23. Do you believe that you have received sufficient training to raise awareness about soil pollution?	0	0	0	0	171	49.7	182	53.2	173	50.3	160	46.8	1.50	1.53
24. Do you believe that you have received enough education to raise awareness about ecological balance?	0	0	0	0	185	53.8	182	53.2	159	46.2	160	46.8	1.54	1.53
Total	$N_{\text{Nigeria}}=344$ $N_{\text{Turkey}}=342$												1.51	1.51

